

Received-Makale Geliş Tarihi 26.04.2025
Published-Yayınlanma Tarihi 31.07.2025
Volume-Cilt (Issue-Sayı), ss/pp 12 (121),1590-1596

Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.16783803/

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ROR Id: <https://ror.org/013s3zh21>

Social Entrepreneurship: A Study on University Students

Sosyal Girişimcilik: Üniversite Öğrencileri Üzerinde Bir Araştırma

ABSTRACT

Social entrepreneurship is a type of entrepreneurship that prefers to offer socially comprehensive solutions and operates with non-profit or sustainable profit models. These university-based entrepreneurs represent a key target audience because they represent both young dynamism and future leaders. This article explores the characteristics of social entrepreneurship at the university under consideration. The research performance was conducted on a total of 202 students studying at the Faculty of Applied Sciences at Necmettin Erbakan University. Analysis of the data obtained from the research reveals that education is the most influential factor in the emergence of social entrepreneurship, while family income is also quite important.

Keywords: Social Entrepreneurship, University Students

ÖZET

Sosyal girişimcilik; toplumsal sorunlara yenilikçi çözümler sunmayı hedefleyen, kar amacı gütmeyen ya da sürdürülebilir kar modelleriyle çalışan girişimcilik türüdür. Bu bağlamda üniversite öğrencileri, hem genç nüfusun dinamizmini hem de geleceğin liderlerini temsil ettikleri için önemli bir hedef kitledir. Bu makalede sosyal girişimcilik kavramı ele alınmış olup üniversite öğrencilerinin sosyal girişimcilik özellikleri araştırılmıştır. Araştırmanın ölçeği Necmettin Erbakan Üniversitesi Uygulamalı Bilimler Fakültesi'nde eğitim gören toplam 202 öğrenciye uygulanmıştır. Araştırmadan elde edilen verilerin analizi sonucunda sosyal girişimcilikte eğitim düzeyinin en etkili faktör olduğu görülürken, ailenin gelir düzeyinin de oldukça önemli olduğu anlaşılmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sosyal Girişimcilik, Üniversite Öğrencileri

1. INTRODUCTION

The general purpose of businesses is to provide benefits to society and corporate social responsibility activities, which have now become a term in today's terminology, have led to social entrepreneurs who are concerned about the problems of society and who try to produce new ideas and implement them to find solutions to these problems, and social enterprises have emerged in this activity carried out by them. Many factors such as the increase in the world population, social and economic changes, wars, and the climate crisis have increased the importance of social entrepreneurship activities. People who adopt the mission of creating and sustaining social value, who notice new opportunities to serve this mission, and who constantly engage in innovation, adaptation and learning processes as a follower of these missions, who act without being limited by the resources at hand, who take risks, and who exhibit a high sense of accountability towards the segments served and the results created are called social entrepreneurs (Dees, 1998). Social entrepreneurship is the creation of applicable socio-economic structures, relations, institutions, organizations and practices that produce and sustain social benefits (Fowler, 2000). In social entrepreneurship, disadvantaged groups within the society can be the target audience, or a large-scale social initiative can be implemented based on a general problem within the society, targeting a significant segment or the entire society (Martin and Osberg, 2007). Social entrepreneurs combine their vision with realism while creating new opportunities by offering innovative ideas. At the same time, social entrepreneurs exhibit creative and ethical behaviors while solving problems. They present ideas for change within the society depending on the mission they undertake (Bornstein, 1998). The difference between social entrepreneurship and other types of entrepreneurship is that social entrepreneurship focuses on

achieving a social mission, which is clearly seen in the context of the social component and its results (El Ebrashi, 2013). The purpose of this research is to determine how the phenomenon of social entrepreneurship, which has great importance in creating value for the society and providing social benefit, is perceived by university students who are candidate entrepreneurs.

2. SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Social entrepreneurship refers to innovative activity with a social purpose, either in the for-profit sector, such as in social purpose commercial enterprises or corporate social entrepreneurship, or across sectors, such as in hybrid structural forms mixing for-profit and non-profit approaches (Noruzi et al., 2010). Social entrepreneurship is an innovative, social value-creating activity that can occur within non-profit organizations, businesses or the public sector, thereby creating new, sustainable socio-economic structures, relationships, institutions, organizations and practices that generate and sustain social benefits (Austin et al., 2006; Bhawe et al., 2006). Social entrepreneurship is the use of entrepreneurial behavior for social purposes rather than for profit, or the use of profits for the benefit of a particular disadvantaged group (Hibbert et al., 2001). We view social entrepreneurship as a process of creating value by combining resources in new ways. Second, these resource combinations primarily aim to discover and exploit opportunities to create social value by promoting social change or meeting social needs. Third, viewed as a process, social entrepreneurship involves providing services and products, but can also refer to the creation of new organizations (Mair and Marti, 2006). “Social entrepreneurship is practiced when a person or group (Peredo and McLean, 2006):

- 1) Purposes, either exclusively or at least explicitly, the creation of social value
- 2) Demonstrates the capacity to recognize and exploit opportunities to create that value
- 3) Uses innovations ranging from outright invention to adaptation of someone else’s innovation in creating and/or distributing social value;
- (4) Is willing to accept an above-average degree of risk in creating and distributing social value;
- (5) Is unusually resourceful in pursuing their social enterprise, relatively undeterred by limited assets.

Social entrepreneurs create social value by using innovation and financial resources, whatever the source, for social, economic, and community development. The expectation that nonprofit organizations will provide services and achieve social change on a larger scale, while also diversifying their funding sources, motivates social entrepreneurs to invent organizations that are hybrids of nonprofit and for-profit structures. The innovations of social entrepreneurs and the organizational models they create offer new perspectives and requires answers (Reis, 1999). In addition, entrepreneurs are also affected by social entrepreneurship and bonding social capital types (Afkari and Arıcıoğlu, 2023). Today, due to the rapidly changing technology, innovation in social entrepreneurship, which requires innovation and change, is identified with innovation and integrated with entrepreneurship, and is also an important factor for success in social entrepreneurship (Karagöz and Yıldırım, 2023).

A social entrepreneur is a person who has high awareness and the potential to solve community-based problems and who creates new applications to solve these problems (Jehan et al., 2020). The passion of social entrepreneurs will enable them to have an efficient entrepreneurship process in terms of time and energy (Adıgüzel and Küçüköğlü, 2020). Social entrepreneurs can be individuals or groups or organizations formed to create change that breaks the mold. Social entrepreneurs aim for sustainable, large-scale change with high social impact. In social entrepreneurship, ideas that break the mold are developed about what to do and how to do it to address important social problems. Social entrepreneurs, with their business skills are an important source of innovation as actors who identify underutilized resources and create new welfare services by combining them (Gerlach, 2006). Social entrepreneurs exist in all sectors. Social entrepreneurs do not need to enter social entrepreneurship or use market-based instruments to be successful. Social entrepreneurship should not be seen as a financing strategy and should not be tied to the idea of business ventures. Entrepreneurship is essentially about establishing new and better ways to create value. The size of a social enterprise can vary greatly among individuals and organizations. Some social entrepreneurs are more entrepreneurial than others, while others may limit their entrepreneurial activities to a specific program or unit. The intensity of social entrepreneurship may decrease over time as conditions change (Noruzi et al., 2010). Social entrepreneurs play a role as change agents in the social sector. Social entrepreneurs (Dess, 1998):

- Embrace the mission of creating and sustaining social value and recognize and pursue new opportunities to serve this mission.
- Engage in a process of continuous innovation, adaptation and learning.
- Use existing resources.

3. METHOD

In the research, the survey method, one of the quantitative research methods, was applied. The survey study was conducted as a result of delivering online surveys to students studying at the Faculty of Applied Sciences of Necmettin Erbakan University between March 2024 and June 2024. 202 students studying in five departments at the Faculty of Applied Sciences; Banking and Financial Management, Logistics Management, Accounting and Financial Management, International Trade and Management Information Systems participated. The Turkish adaptation of the scale developed by Soba and Yıldız (2020) by Capella Peris, Gomez, Puig, and Bernardo (2020) was used. First of all, questions about the demographic characteristics of the participants were asked in the survey. The Social Entrepreneurship scale consists of 30 dimensions and six factors.

4. FINDINGS

As seen in Table 1, when the demographic characteristics of the participants were evaluated, it was determined that the majority of the participants were female (63.4%), between the ages of 21-23 (62.4%), generally 4th grade students (40.6%) and the monthly income of the family was 35000 TL and above (23.8%).

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Demographic Characteristics		Frequency	Percent
Gender			
	Female	128	63,4
	Male	74	36,6
Age			
	18-20 years old	40	19,8
	21-23 years old	126	62,4
	24-26 years old	22	10,9
	27-29 years old	2	1
	30-35 years old	2	1
	36-40 years old	4	2
	41 years old and above	6	3
Grade			
	1st Grade	48	23,8
	2nd Grade	32	15,8
	3rd Grade	40	19,8
	4th Grade	82	40,6
Family Monthly Income Status			
	0-10000 TL	26	12,9
	10000-15000 TL	38	18,8
	15000-20000 TL	38	18,8
	20000-25000 TL	18	8,9
	25000-30000 TL	24	11,9
	30000-35000 TL	10	5
	35000 TL and above	48	23,8
Total		202	100

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Social Entrepreneurship Scale

Item	Mean	St. Deviation
I believe that I can handle most problematic situations.	3,84	0,94
I am determined to achieve my goals.	4,18	0,89
I believe that taking risks is necessary to move forward.	4,18	0,87
I always look for the positive side in bad situations.	3,48	1,03
I like taking calculated risks with new ideas.	3,88	0,83
I think that people who take risks are more likely to succeed than those who don't.	4,14	0,92
I can do something creatively, in a different way than others.	3,84	0,95
I do every task given to me as well as I can.	4,24	0,88
I prefer to be a leader when working in groups.	3,83	1,09
I like to help my friends/classmates.	4,17	0,88
People who help others are role models to follow.	4,16	0,89
I can take responsibility for the consequences of what I say.	4,30	0,82
I usually perform very well in any job role or projects I participate in.	4,00	0,90
I believe that I can handle most problematic situations.	4,09	0,85
I prefer to work for free in non-governmental organizations/organizations.	3,63	1,02
I analyze the mistakes I make and learn from them.	4,00	0,90
I think of new benefits for common goals.	4,00	0,82
I work harmoniously with my colleagues/coworkers on joint projects.	4,18	0,75
I am seriously considering starting my own business after finishing my education.	3,58	1,17
I have been involved in some group projects/collaborations.	3,97	0,99
I believe in my potential for entrepreneurship.	3,83	1,05
Working together can solve problems through dialogue.	3,95	2,03
I can create and benefit from business opportunities.	4,24	4,08
I prefer working in environments with more people.	3,80	0,95
I enjoy finding effective solutions to problems before anyone else discovers them.	4,06	0,80
I believe that opportunities can be extracted from problems or difficult situations.	4,12	0,72
I can create suggestions to improve projects; I participate in this.	4,11	0,66
I like to coordinate other people in collaborative work.	3,96	0,94
I am good at dealing with unforeseen situations.	3,85	0,89
When plans change, I do my job by improvising without difficulty.	3,90	0,93
General Average	3,98	0,56

When the participants' responses to the items of the social entrepreneurship scale were evaluated, it was observed that they agreed at a high level with the statements "I can take responsibility for the consequences of what I say." (Average=4.30; S.D.=0.82), "I do every task given to me as well as I can." (Average=4.24; S.D.=0.88) and "I can create business opportunities and take advantage of them." (Average=4.24; S.D.=4.08).

As seen in Table 3, the reliability analysis of the social entrepreneurship scale consisting of 30 items was calculated through the Cronbach Alpha (α) value. The reliability coefficient is $\alpha=0.933$. This value shows that the internal consistency coefficient of the social entrepreneurship scale is high ($\alpha>0.7$).

Table 3. Reliability Analysis of Social Entrepreneurship Scale

Scale	Mean	Standard Deviation	Number of Items	Cronbach Alpha (α)
Social Entrepreneurship	119,50	16,84	30	0,933

Table 4- Social Entrepreneurship Scale-Related Social Analysis

Personal Characteristics of Entrepreneurship (1)	1	2	3	4	5	6
I believe that I can handle most problematic situations.	0,784					
I always look for the positive aspects of bad situations.	0,443					
I think that people who take risks are more likely to succeed than those who don't.	0,331					
I take responsibility for the consequences of what I say.	0,627					
I do every task given to me as well as possible.	0,407					
I am seriously considering starting my own business after I finish my education.	0,807					
I can do something creatively, differently than others.	0,652					
Innovation and Collaboration in Entrepreneurship (2)						
I like to coordinate other people in collaborative work.		0,556				
I have been involved in some group projects/collaborations.		0,591				
I think of new benefits for common goals.		0,779				
I usually perform very well in any work role or project I participate in.		0,702				
Problems in working together can be solved through dialogue.		0,551				
Social Characteristics of Entrepreneurship and Risk Taking (3)						
I am good at dealing with unforeseen situations.			0,543			
I can create and take advantage of business opportunities.			0,693			
I believe that I can handle most problematic situations.			0,718			
I analyze my mistakes and learn from them.			0,781			
I believe that taking risks is necessary to move forward.			0,401			
I like to take calculated risks with new ideas.			0,674			
Adaptation and Overcoming in Entrepreneurship (4)						
I work harmoniously with my colleagues/coworkers on joint projects.				0,822		
I believe that opportunities can emerge from problems or difficult situations.				0,767		
I like to coordinate other people in collaborative work.				0,596		
I do my job by improvising without difficulty when plans change.				0,594		
Helping and Self-Confidence in Entrepreneurship (5)						
I like to help my friends/classmates.					0,708	
People who help others are role models to follow.					0,57	
I prefer to work in environments with more people.					0,551	
I believe in my potential in entrepreneurship.					0,768	
Problem Solving and Leadership in Entrepreneurship (6)						
I enjoy finding effective solutions to problems before anyone else has discovered them.						0,314
I prefer to work for non-governmental organizations/organizations for free.						0,701
I can create suggestions to improve projects; I participate in this.						0,49
Explained Variance						0,671
Total Explained Variance	10,859	2,212	1,813	1,528	1,389	1,20
KMO and Bartlett's Test	63,336					
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	0,851					
Personal Characteristics of Entrepreneurship (1)	3752,272					
p	0,00					

As seen in Table 4, in order to determine the structural validity of the social entrepreneurship scale, exploratory factor analysis was applied using principal component analysis and "Direct Oblimin" axis rotation technique. As a result of exploratory factor analysis, it was determined that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sample adequacy was 0.851 and the sample size was sufficient for factor analysis. The significance of Bartlett's sphericity test ($\chi^2=3752.272$; $p<.001$) means that the correlation relations between the items are suitable for factor analysis. In the analysis, factors with eigenvalues greater than 1 were formed. In the analysis, items with factor loadings less than 0.30 were not evaluated. As a result of the rotation process in the exploratory factor analysis, it was determined that the scale was gathered under six factors. The first factor explains social entrepreneurship by 10.859%, the second factor by 2.212%, the third factor by 1.813%, the fourth factor by 1.528%, the fifth factor by 1.389% and the sixth factor by 1.20%. Based on the items collected under the six factors and the relevant literature, these factors were named as personal characteristics of entrepreneurship, innovation and cooperation in entrepreneurship, social characteristics and risk taking in entrepreneurship, adaptation and overcoming in entrepreneurship, helpfulness and self-confidence in entrepreneurship, problem solving and leadership in entrepreneurship. These results indicate the validity of the six-factor structure of the social entrepreneurship scale consisting of 30 questions. The existence of a correlation between the obtained factor structures and demographic variables was investigated with Pearson correlation analysis and the results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Correlation Analysis Results Between Factors and Demographic Variables

		Your Gender	Your Age	Your Grade	What is your family's monthly income status?
f1	Correlation Coefficient	.076	.079	,227**	,191**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.282	.266	.001	.006
	N	202	202	202	202
f2	Correlation Coefficient	.103	.030	.105	.066
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.145	.672	.135	.348
	N	202	202	202	202
f3	Correlation Coefficient	,206**	.105	,147*	,152*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.135	.036	.031
	N	202	202	202	202
f4	Correlation Coefficient	.112	.001	,208**	.103
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.113	.983	.003	.144
	N	202	202	202	202
f5	Correlation Coefficient	.054	.083	,163*	.103
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.442	.243	.020	.144
	N	202	202	202	202
f6	Correlation Coefficient	.135	.060	,157*	.073
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.056	.397	.026	.300
	N	202	202	202	202

*With a 5% margin of error **With a 1% margin of error

According to the results obtained, it is understood that there is a significant positive relationship between the gender variable and only the 3rd Factor (Personal Characteristics Regarding Entrepreneurship). Since the gender question is analyzed with the code of female 1 and male 2, the increase in the 3rd Factor is higher in men. No significant relationship was found between the age variable and the factors. It was determined that there was a positive significant relationship between the grade of the participants in the survey and other factors except the 2nd Factor. According to this determination, as the grades of the students participating in the survey increase; Personal Characteristics Regarding Entrepreneurship, Social Characteristics and Risk-Taking Regarding Entrepreneurship, Adaptability and Overcoming in Entrepreneurship, Helpfulness and Self-Confidence in Entrepreneurship and Problem Solving and Leadership characteristics increase. A positive significant relationship was found between the family income level of the participants in the survey and the 1st and 2nd Factors. According to this finding, as the family income level increases, Personal Characteristics of Entrepreneurship and Innovation and Cooperation in Entrepreneurship increase.

5. CONCLUSION

In order to investigate the relationship between the sub-factors created in the measurement of social entrepreneurship competence and the demographic structures of individuals studying in higher education, 202 students studying in higher education participated in this study. It was determined that the majority of the students participating in the study were female (%63.4), between the ages of 21-23 (%62.4), generally 4th grade students (%40.6) and the monthly income of the family was 35000 TL and above (%23.8). In addition, it was determined that the scale created with the survey research consisted of 6 factors (Personal Characteristics Regarding Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Cooperation in Entrepreneurship, Social Characteristics and Risk-Taking Regarding Entrepreneurship, Adaptability and Overcoming in Entrepreneurship, Helpfulness and Self-Confidence in Entrepreneurship and Problem Solving and Leadership in Entrepreneurship). The values of these six factors were calculated by adding the survey values of each question forming the factor. The calculated values of each factor and the demographic variable values were tried to be determined by correlation analysis. According to the correlation analysis results, Personal Characteristics Regarding Entrepreneurship have a positive and significant relationship with the students' class and family income level. According to this result, as the students' class increases and their family income level increases, their entrepreneurial characteristics increase. No significant relationship was found between the Innovation and Cooperation factor in Entrepreneurship and demographic variables. A positive and significant relationship was found between the Social Characteristics and Risk-Taking factor regarding Entrepreneurship and the variables of gender, class and family income level. According to this determination, social characteristics and risk-taking regarding entrepreneurship are significantly higher in men. In addition, it was understood that these characteristics increase as the students' classes and family income levels increase. A significant positive relationship was found between the Adaptability and Overcoming factor in Entrepreneurship and the student's grade level. According to this determination, as the student's grade increases, the adaptability and overcoming feature in entrepreneurship increases. A significant positive relationship was found between the Helpfulness and Self-Confidence factor in Entrepreneurship and the student's grade level. According to this determination,

as the student's grade increases, the characteristics of helpfulness and self-confidence in entrepreneurship increase. A significant positive relationship was found between the Problem Solving and Leadership factor in Entrepreneurship and the grade of the student. According to this determination, as the student's grade increases, the characteristics of problem solving and leadership in entrepreneurship increase. Depending on these determinations, while the level of education is the most effective factor in social entrepreneurship, it is understood that the income level of the family is also very important.

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